

Generational Differences in Volunteerism: A Comparative Analysis of Younger and Older Adults in Koronadal City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study examined generational differences in volunteerism between youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60 years old and above) in Koronadal City, Philippines. Guided by the Functionalist Theory of Volunteerism, a quantitative-comparative and correlational research design was employed. Using stratified sampling, 120 respondents (60 youth and 60 older adults) participated in the study. Data were gathered through a validated, researcher-made questionnaire measuring demographic profile, levels of volunteerism, and motivations for engagement. Descriptive statistics, independent samples t-tests, and multiple regression analyses were applied. Findings revealed that both youth and older adults demonstrated an overall agreeable level of volunteerism, with youth more engaged in environmental and disaster-related initiatives, while older adults were more active in faith-based and community outreach programs. However, t-test results indicated no statistically significant differences in volunteerism levels between the two groups. Similarly, regression analysis showed that demographic variables such as sex, educational attainment, and income were not significant predictors of volunteerism. These findings suggest that while descriptive patterns vary, both generations equally contribute to community engagement, underscoring the need for inclusive volunteer programs that harness the strengths of all age groups.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Volunteerism is widely recognized as a critical driver of social cohesion, civic engagement, and sustainable development across the globe. According to the United Nations Volunteers (UNV, 2022), approximately 862 million people aged 15 and older participate in volunteer activities every month, with the Asia-Pacific region registering a 17.2% participation rate—higher than the global average of 15%. Informal volunteerism, such as community help outside formal organizations, is

more prevalent worldwide at 14.3% compared to 6.5% for formal volunteering (UNV, 2022). These contributions are integral to advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with the UNV program deploying nearly 13,000 volunteers in 2023, of which 64% served within their own countries (United Nations Volunteers, 2023). Recent trends highlight the increasing role of digital volunteerism and micro-volunteering, enabling individuals—especially younger generations—to contribute through short, flexible, and often online engagements (Smith & Cordery, 2021). These global shifts signal both continuity and innovation in how communities mobilize human resources for collective benefit.

In the Philippine context, volunteerism has long been embedded in cultural practices, particularly through the bayanihan tradition of mutual help. Even amidst the global decline in generosity during 2024, the Philippines ranked fourth in the world for volunteer participation, with 44% of adults reporting they had volunteered in the previous month (Flores, 2025). The Philippine National Volunteer Service Coordinating Agency (PNVSCA), mandated by Republic Act No. 9418 or the Volunteer Act of 2007, continues to strengthen partnerships among government agencies, civil society organizations, educational institutions, and the private sector to promote volunteerism across the country. The 2024 PNVSCA Annual Report highlights notable progress in expanding community-driven initiatives, enhancing capacity-building programs, and implementing the National Volunteer Deployment Framework, underscoring the government's sustained commitment to volunteer service (Philippine National Volunteer Service Coordinating Agency [PNVSCA], 2025). This growth is bolstered by national programs such as the Bayanihang Bayan Program and the National Volunteering Strategy, which integrate volunteerism into key development priorities, including education, environmental conservation, disaster response, and health services (PNVSCA, 2023). These national-level initiatives demonstrate the government's commitment to formalizing and scaling volunteer engagement as part of inclusive growth strategies.

At the local level, Koronadal City reflects a dynamic yet underexplored landscape of volunteerism. While no empirical studies have systematically examined patterns, motivations, or generational differences among volunteers, recent initiatives provide insight into community engagement. For example, the “Buliganay Pantry” volunteer effort in April 2021 mobilized civic-minded residents to provide food assistance during the pandemic, illustrating grassroots responsiveness (Mindanao Life, 2021). Similarly, a medical mission in June 2025 engaged 46 volunteer health professionals to deliver free services to 444 residents across age groups (Gold Star Daily News, 2025). Youth-led service is also evident in the July 2024 bloodletting activity, organized by the Rotaract Club of Koronadal in partnership with civic and health institutions (Rotaract Club of Koronadal, 2024). Although such examples show active volunteer engagement—often short-term and event-related—they have not been systematically studied, especially with regard to differing motivations or participation patterns between younger (15–30 years) and older (60+ years) volunteers. This lack of localized, generational research within Koronadal City highlights a critical gap that this study seeks to fill.

The state of the art in volunteerism research underscores the need to consider generational differences in motivations, forms of participation, and socio-economic predictors. International studies have shown that younger volunteers often prioritize personal growth, career development, and skill acquisition, while older volunteers tend to emphasize altruism, community belonging,

and social contribution (Chacón et al., 2017; Okun & Michel, 2019). In Southeast Asia, few empirical works have addressed these contrasts, and in the Philippine setting, most studies focus on national-level trends or specific volunteer sectors rather than cross-generational comparisons in a localized environment. This gap in the literature becomes more pronounced in regional urban centers like Koronadal City, where demographic diversity and cultural dynamics could influence volunteer behavior differently from metropolitan areas.

Given these realities, the research gap lies in the lack of localized, age-specific volunteerism studies that integrate demographic predictors with participation patterns and motivations. Without such data, policymakers, non-profits, and community leaders are unable to design targeted interventions that maximize the contributions of both youth and older adults. This study is therefore necessary not only to expand theoretical knowledge on generational volunteerism but also to produce practical insights for community development planning.

The primary objective of this study is to examine the generational differences in volunteerism among youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60 years old and above) in Koronadal City. Specifically, it seeks to compare their levels of participation, types of activities, years of experience, motivations, and the predictive value of demographic factors such as sex, educational attainment, and monthly income. Through this localized, comparative approach, the study aims to contribute to both scholarly discourse and practical policymaking, fostering a stronger, more inclusive volunteer culture in the city.

Literature Review

Volunteerism and Well-Being

Volunteerism has been widely documented as a contributor to individual and community well-being. Nichol et al. (2023) found that engaging in at least one hour of structured volunteering per week improved older adults' life satisfaction, purpose, and personal growth. Similarly, Węziak-Białowska et al. (2024), through a Campbell systematic review, concluded that volunteering among older adults is consistently linked to better mental health, reduced mortality, and improved functional capacity. More recently, Huang (2019) highlighted that continued volunteering after retirement fosters higher quality of life and psychosocial resilience, while Tabassum et al. (2016) demonstrated that such engagement may even slow biological aging through positive effects on epigenetic markers.

Motivations for Volunteer Engagement

Understanding why people volunteer is critical to sustaining engagement. Fernandes & De Matos (2023), in a meta-analysis using the Volunteer Functions Inventory, identified six key motivational domains—values, understanding, enhancement, career, social, and protective—with older adults prioritizing value-based motivations and younger adults focusing more on career and skill development. Cox et al. (2018) reinforced this distinction, noting that intrinsic motivations such as personal growth and altruism drive long-term involvement, whereas extrinsic motivations are more

prominent among youth, particularly for career advancement and networking. These differences imply the need for age-sensitive volunteer recruitment strategies (Petrovic & Stukas, 2021).

Socio-Demographic Predictors of Volunteerism

Demographic factors play a significant role in shaping volunteer behavior. Chen et al. (2024) demonstrated that higher educational attainment strongly predicts sustained volunteering, while income and gender effects are more context-dependent. Mak & Fancourt (2020), analyzing longitudinal Swiss data, confirmed that individuals with greater human capital, particularly university education, are more likely to participate in formal volunteer activities, although work-related time constraints can limit engagement. Such findings underscore the importance of considering socio-economic resources in volunteer program planning.

Trends and Patterns in Volunteer Participation

Recent evidence indicates shifts in the types and formats of volunteer activities. Eimhjellen et al. (2018) and Rochester (2021) observed a generational divide, with younger adults gravitating toward short-term, event-based opportunities and skill-building roles, while older adults favor sustained, relationship-centered commitments. Vansuch (2017) argued that these patterns reflect both life-stage priorities and the influence of evolving civic participation models. With emerging global challenges and digital volunteerism platforms, volunteer engagement is diversifying, creating new opportunities but also requiring tailored retention approaches.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Functionalist Theory of Volunteerism developed by Clary et al. (1998), which explains that individuals engage in volunteer activities to fulfill specific psychological and social needs. The theory identifies six primary motivational functions: values (altruism), understanding (acquiring knowledge and skills), social (building relationships), career (gaining job-related experience), protective (addressing personal challenges or reducing guilt), and enhancement (improving self-esteem and personal growth).

In the context of this study, the Functionalist Theory serves as a lens to explore the generational differences in motivations and patterns of volunteerism in Koronadal City. Younger adults (18–30 years old) may be more inclined toward motivations related to skill development, career advancement, and social connections, while older adults (60 years old and above) may prioritize altruism, values, and enhancement functions that align with long-term community involvement.

By focusing on the functional motivations of volunteers, this framework directly supports the investigation of differences in frequency, type, years of experience, and scope of involvement between youth and older adults. It also provides a basis for understanding how demographic factors (sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income) might influence these motivations and levels of engagement.

Conceptual Framework

Guided by the Functionalist Theory of Volunteerism (Clary et al., 1998), this study compares the volunteerism of youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60 years old and above) in Koronadal City. The framework examines three core variables for each group: demographic profile (sex, age, highest educational attainment, monthly income), level of volunteerism (frequency, type, years of experience, scope of involvement), and motivations (personal growth, social connection, altruism, skill development, career advancement).

The model illustrates how these variables interact within and between generations to identify significant differences in volunteerism. Additionally, demographic factors are treated as predictors of volunteerism levels, providing insights into how personal and socio-economic characteristics influence engagement in volunteer activities across generations.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Paradigm

Research Objectives

Generally, this study aims to examine the generational differences in volunteerism among youth and older adults in Koronadal City, and specifically seeks to attain the following;

1. Determine the demographic profile of youth and older adult respondents involved in volunteerism activities in Koronadal City in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Age
 - c. Highest Educational attainment
 - d. And monthly income
2. Assess the overall level of volunteerism among youth in Koronadal City in terms of:
 - a. Frequency of participation
 - b. Type of volunteer activities

- c. Volunteer experience
 - d. And scope of involvement
3. Assess the overall level of volunteerism among older adults in Koronadal City in terms of:
 - a. Frequency of participation
 - b. Type of volunteer activities
 - c. Years of volunteer experience
 - d. And scope of involvement
4. Identify the common motivations for volunteering among youth and older adults in terms of:
 - a. Personal growth,
 - b. Social connection,
 - c. Altruism,
 - d. Skill development,
 - e. And career advancement
5. Determine if there is a significant difference in the level of volunteerism between youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60+ years old) in Koronadal City.
6. Examine the extent to which demographic factors (sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income) predict the level of volunteerism within each age group (youth and older adults) in Koronadal City.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the level of volunteerism between youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60+ years old) in Koronadal City.

H₀₂: Demographic factors (sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income) do not significantly predict the level of volunteerism within each age group (youth and older adults) in Koronadal City.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative-comparative and correlational research design. The comparative aspect is appropriate because the study seeks to determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of volunteerism between two distinct generational groups—youth aged 18–30 years and older adults aged 60 years and above—in Koronadal City (Creswell, 2014). Comparative research is suitable for analyzing differences between groups based on measured variables, particularly when both groups share a common experience such as volunteerism (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2012).

The correlational component will be used to examine the extent to which demographic factors—specifically sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income—predict the level of volunteerism within each age group. Correlational research is appropriate when determining the degree and direction of relationships among variables without manipulating them (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2019).

By combining these approaches, the study both compared generational differences and identified predictive relationships, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of volunteerism patterns across age groups. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire and analyzed through descriptive statistics, independent samples t-tests, and multiple regression analysis to address the stated objectives.

Respondents and Sampling Technique

The respondents comprise two strata of community volunteers residing in Koronadal City, Philippines: (a) youth aged 18–30 years, and (b) older adults aged 60 years and above. Respondents are individuals who have engaged in any organized or community-based volunteer activity within the past 12 months. The inclusion criteria are as follows: (1) resident of Koronadal City; (2) belongs to either age stratum (18–30; 60+); (3) has participated in volunteer activities within the last year; and (4) able and willing to provide informed consent (for minors, assent with parental/guardian consent). The exclusion criteria include: (1) non-residents; (2) absence of volunteer activity in the last 12 months; and (3) inability to complete the questionnaire. Potential respondents will be identified through local NGOs and civic groups (e.g., Red Cross chapters, church/community outreach, Rotary/Lions, barangay committees, school/university volunteer programs, senior citizens' associations). Permissions will be sought from organization focal persons to circulate the survey. Since the total population size is unknown, Cochran's formula for an unknown population with a 10% margin of error and a 95% confidence level was used, resulting in a base sample of approximately 96 respondents. A 20% allowance for non-response increases the target to 120 respondents, equally allocated between the two strata (60 youth and 60 older adults). Stratified sampling by age group was employed. Where full lists were unavailable, quota sampling was applied within each stratum, with simple random selection used whenever rosters were provided. Participation was voluntary and anonymous; informed consent (and assent for minors) was obtained. No identifying information was reported, and respondents could withdraw at any time without consequence.

Research Instrument

The primary research instrument was a researcher-made survey questionnaire designed to address all specific objectives in sequence. It comprised four sections aligned with the study objectives and was validated by experts in research methodology, social sciences, and volunteerism to ensure content validity. The questionnaire included close-ended questions, multiple-choice items, and Likert-scale ratings for quantitative analysis. Section 1 gathered the respondents' demographic profile—sex, age, highest educational attainment, and monthly income—as descriptive data and potential predictors of volunteerism. Section 2 measured the

level of volunteerism among youth (15–30 years) through items on participation frequency, types of activities, years of experience, and scope of involvement. Section 3 mirrored Section 2 for older adults (60+ years) to enable direct group comparisons. Section 4 assessed motivations for volunteering, based on the Functionalist Theory of Volunteerism, across five domains: personal growth, social connection, altruism, skill development, and career advancement. A 5-point Likert scale based on Joshi et al. (2015) was used to quantify agreement levels. The structured format allowed measurement of generational differences and the predictive role of demographic factors. Before data collection, the instrument underwent pilot testing for clarity, reliability, and suitability, with revisions made based on expert feedback and pilot results.

Table 1. Interpretation of Mean Scores for the 5-Point Likert Scale

Numerical Rating	Range of Means	Verbal Description
5	4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.40-4.19	Agree
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral
2	1.80-2.59	Disagree
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

Based from: (Joshi et al., 2015).

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure followed a sequential, waterfall approach to ensure systematic collection and analysis. First, the research objectives and variables were clearly defined based on the stated research questions and hypotheses. A structured researcher-made questionnaire, incorporating a 5-point Likert scale adapted from Joshi et al. (2015), was developed to capture demographic profiles, volunteerism levels, and motivations among youth (15–30 years) and older adults (60+ years) in Koronadal City. The instrument underwent expert validation and pilot testing to ensure clarity, reliability, and content accuracy. Respondents were identified through local NGOs, civic groups, and community organizations, applying stratified sampling by age group and, when necessary, quota sampling. After securing organizational permissions and informed consent (or assent for minors), surveys were distributed, ensuring anonymity and voluntary participation. Completed questionnaires were retrieved, screened, and cleaned for accuracy before statistical analysis.

Statistical Analysis and Treatment

Data collected from the validated survey questionnaires were encoded, cleaned, and analyzed using SPSS v23 statistical software. **Descriptive statistics**—such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations—were used to summarize the demographic profile of respondents (sex, age, highest educational attainment, and monthly income) and to describe their level of volunteerism and motivations (Objectives 1–4). To determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of volunteerism between youth (15–30 years) and older adults

(60+ years) in Koronadal City (Objective 5), an **independent samples t-test** was employed. To examine the predictive influence of demographic factors (sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income) on volunteerism within each age group (Objective 6), **multiple regression analysis** (as dependent variable was treated as continuous variable; mean of ordinal items) was conducted, allowing for the estimation of the strength and direction of relationships. All tests were evaluated at a 0.05 significance level, and results were interpreted in relation to the study's hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents- Sex

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	70	58.3	58.3	58.3
Male	50	41.7	41.7	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

The data (Table 2) show that females (58.3%) outnumber males (41.7%) among the respondents. This suggests that women are slightly more engaged in volunteerism activities in Koronadal City, which may influence the patterns of participation and motivations observed in the study. Since sex is one of the key demographic factors under investigation, this imbalance highlights the need to consider how gender roles and expectations might shape differences in volunteer experience and motivations between youth and older adults.

Table 3. Demographic Profile of the Respondents- Age Bracket

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-30 (Youth)	60	50.0	50.0	50.0
60+ (Older Adult)	60	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows that the respondents were equally divided between youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60 years and above), each comprising 50% of the total sample (n=120). This equal allocation reflects the use of stratified sampling with quotas to ensure balanced representation across generational cohorts. Such a design aligns with the study's objective of comparing youth and older adults' volunteerism in Koronadal City, enabling valid cross-group analyses on participation frequency, type of activities, years of experience, motivations, and demographic predictors.

Table 4. Highest Educational Attainment

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid College	29	24.2	24.2	24.2
Elementary	13	10.8	10.8	35.0
Junior High	27	22.5	22.5	57.5
Postgraduate	9	7.5	7.5	65.0

Senior High	32	26.7	26.7	91.7
TVET/NC	10	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 reveals that respondents had varied educational backgrounds, with the largest share having completed Senior High School (26.7%), followed by College (24.2%) and Junior High School (22.5%). Smaller proportions attained Elementary education (10.8%), TVET/NC qualifications (8.3%), or Postgraduate studies (7.5%). This distribution highlights that most volunteers come from middle to higher levels of education, suggesting that educational exposure may play a role in encouraging community engagement. The diversity in attainment also supports the study’s aim of examining how demographic factors, such as education, may influence the extent and nature of volunteerism across youth and older adults in Koronadal City

Table 5. Monthly Income

	Frequency	Percent
Below 5,000	14	11.7
5,000–9,999	23	19.2
10,000–19,999	33	27.5
20,000–39,999	23	19.2
40,000–69,999	21	17.5
70,000 and above	6	5.0
Total	120	100.0

Table 5 indicates that the majority of respondents earn within the ₱10,000–19,999 income bracket (27.5%), followed by those in the ₱5,000–9,999 (19.2%) and ₱20,000–39,999 (19.2%) ranges. A considerable share also reported incomes between ₱40,000–69,999 (17.5%), while smaller proportions fall under the below ₱5,000 (11.7%) and ₱70,000 and above (5.0%) categories. This distribution suggests that most volunteers come from low- to middle-income groups, reflecting the socioeconomic diversity of participants in volunteerism activities. Such variation in income levels is important in understanding how economic capacity may shape the extent and motivations of volunteering across different segments of the population in Koronadal City.

Table 6. Level of Volunteerism among Youth in Koronadal City

Indicators	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Frequency of Participation (FP)				
FP - I regularly set aside time each month to participate in volunteer activities.	60	3.55	0.91	Agree
FP - In the past year, I joined volunteer activities frequently.	60	3.70	0.79	Agree
FP - I sometimes adjust my schedule to balance volunteering with other priorities.	60	3.45	0.89	Agree

FP - I fulfill my commitments when I agree to join a volunteer activity.	60	3.63	0.92	Agree
FP - My volunteer participation has consistent intervals over time.	60	3.62	0.76	Agree
Weighted Mean (FP)		3.59		Agree
Type of Volunteer Activities (TVA)				
TVA - I participate in environmental activities such as clean-up drives, tree planting, or waste management projects.	60	3.75	0.79	Agree
TVA - I take part in disaster response and relief operations (e.g., food distribution, evacuation assistance, medical missions).	60	3.70	0.81	Agree
TVA - I volunteer in educational programs such as tutoring, mentoring, or literacy campaigns.	60	3.73	0.78	Agree
TVA - I engage in faith-based or community outreach programs organized by churches or civic groups.	60	3.63	0.80	Agree
TVA - I participate in cultural, sports, or fundraising events that support community causes.	60	3.52	0.83	Agree
Weighted Mean (TVA)		3.67		Agree
Volunteer Experience (VE)				
VE - I have been involved in volunteering for several years.	60	3.72	0.85	Agree
VE - My volunteer involvement started recently.	60	3.47	0.85	Agree
VE - I have maintained continuous involvement in volunteering over time.	60	3.72	0.69	Agree
VE - Others recognize my experience in volunteer work.	60	3.50	0.79	Agree
VE - I provide guidance or support to newer volunteers.	60	3.57	0.91	Agree
Weighted Mean (YVE)		3.59		Agree
Scope of Involvement (SI)				
SI - My volunteering includes activities beyond my immediate barangay/community.	60	3.55	0.75	Agree
SI - I have joined projects that serve communities outside Koronadal City.	60	3.63	0.84	Agree
SI - My volunteering is focused within my neighborhood or community.	60	3.72	0.74	Agree
SI - I have collaborated with organizations at the provincial or national level.	60	3.55	0.77	Agree
SI - I am open to volunteering in other places when needed.	60	3.48	0.83	Agree
Weighted Mean (SI)		3.59		Agree

Findings indicate that youth respondents generally show an agreeable level of volunteerism (overall WM = 3.61). Their frequency of participation (WM = 3.59) suggests that while they actively

join volunteer work, their consistency may vary due to competing responsibilities such as school or work. In terms of types of activities (WM = 3.67), youth are most engaged in environmental and disaster-related initiatives, reflecting both responsiveness to urgent community concerns and alignment with causes that resonate with their generation.

The volunteer experience (WM = 3.59) highlights sustained involvement, with some youths already recognized for their service — a nuance that points to emerging leadership but also uneven distribution of active roles. Meanwhile, the scope of involvement (WM = 3.59) shows a balance: most prefer local community work, yet others extend participation beyond Koronadal City, signaling both rootedness in their immediate environment and openness to wider civic action. Taken together, youth volunteerism is dynamic, cause-driven, and community-centered, though moderated by personal constraints and variability in depth of engagement.

Table 7. Level of Volunteerism among Older Adults in Koronadal City

Indicators	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Frequency of Participation (FP)				
FP - I regularly set aside time each month to participate in volunteer activities.	60	3.63	0.69	Agree
FP - In the past year, I joined volunteer activities frequently.	60	3.58	0.89	Agree
FP - I sometimes adjust my schedule to balance volunteering with other priorities.	60	3.55	0.81	Agree
FP - I fulfill my commitments when I agree to join a volunteer activity.	60	3.50	0.89	Agree
FP - My volunteer participation has consistent intervals over time.	60	3.65	0.73	Agree
Weighted Mean (FP)		3.58		Agree
Type of Volunteer Activities (TVA)				
TVA - I participate in environmental activities such as clean-up drives, tree planting, or waste management projects.	60	3.75	0.82	Agree
TVA - I take part in disaster response and relief operations (e.g., food distribution, evacuation assistance, medical missions).	60	3.68	0.91	Agree
TVA - I volunteer in educational programs such as tutoring, mentoring, or literacy campaigns.	60	3.58	0.91	Agree
TVA - I engage in faith-based or community outreach programs organized by churches or civic groups.	60	3.68	0.75	Agree
TVA - I participate in cultural, sports, or fundraising events that support community causes.	60	3.73	0.86	Agree
Weighted Mean (TVA)		3.68		Agree
Volunteer Experience (YVE)				
VE - I have been involved in volunteering for several years.	60	3.70	0.93	Agree

VE - My volunteer involvement started recently.	60	3.78	0.80	Agree
VE - I have maintained continuous involvement in volunteering over time.	60	3.57	0.95	Agree
VE - Others recognize my experience in volunteer work.	60	3.65	0.84	Agree
VE - I provide guidance or support to newer volunteers.	60	3.52	0.79	Agree
Weighted Mean (YVE)		3.64		Agree
Scope of Involvement (SI)				
SI - My volunteering includes activities beyond my immediate barangay/community.	60	3.57	0.79	Agree
SI - I have joined projects that serve communities outside Koronadal City.	60	3.57	0.85	Agree
SI - My volunteering is focused within my neighborhood or community.	60	3.47	0.77	Agree
SI - I have collaborated with organizations at the provincial or national level.	60	3.68	0.75	Agree
SI - I am open to volunteering in other places when needed.	60	3.73	0.80	Agree
Weighted Mean (SI)		3.60		Agree

The results show that older adults in Koronadal City demonstrate a generally agreeable level of volunteerism across all dimensions (overall WM = 3.63). In terms of frequency of participation (WM = 3.58), older adults regularly engage in volunteer activities and sustain their involvement, though their participation is slightly less flexible compared to youth, possibly due to age-related routines or health considerations.

For types of volunteer activities (WM = 3.68), older adults show high engagement in environmental, disaster response, and faith-based/community outreach programs, suggesting that their service is closely tied to collective welfare, moral commitments, and community stability. This highlights a values-driven orientation.

In terms of volunteer experience (WM = 3.64), many older adults have both long-term and recent involvement, pointing to a continuity of civic engagement even later in life. Recognition from others and their role in guiding newer volunteers suggest their status as mentors and repositories of institutional knowledge.

Finally, the scope of involvement (WM = 3.60) indicates that while many are community-focused, older adults also extend their contributions beyond their barangay and even to provincial/national activities, reflecting a broad yet steady civic orientation and a readiness to respond when called upon. Overall, older adults' volunteerism is rooted in experience, community values, and sustained commitment, making them not only active participants but also stabilizing figures in Koronadal City's volunteer landscape.

Table 8. Common Motivations for Volunteering among Youth and Older Adults in Koronadal City

Dimensions / Indicators	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Personal Growth				
M1 - Volunteering helps me discover my strengths.	120	3.60	0.76	Agree
M2 - I volunteer to challenge myself and grow.	120	3.57	0.84	Agree
M3 - Volunteering makes me feel more confident.	120	3.57	0.68	Agree
Weighted Mean (Personal Growth)		3.58		Agree
Social Connection				
M4 - I volunteer to meet new people and build friendships.	120	3.71	0.78	Agree
M5 - Volunteering makes me feel part of a community.	120	3.62	0.66	Agree
M6 - People important to me value my volunteer involvement.	120	3.65	0.73	Agree
Weighted Mean (Social Connection)		3.66		Agree
Altruism				
M7 - I volunteer because I want to help those in need.	120	3.58	0.75	Agree
M8 - I feel responsible for improving my community.	120	3.55	0.74	Agree
M9 - I would still volunteer even if no one noticed.	120	3.79	0.73	Agree
Weighted Mean (Altruism)		3.64		Agree
Skill Development				
M10 - I volunteer to gain practical skills I can use elsewhere.	120	3.51	0.74	Agree
M11 - Volunteering lets me apply what I've learned in school/work.	120	3.74	0.70	Agree
M12 - I seek volunteer roles that develop specific competencies.	120	3.61	0.71	Agree
Weighted Mean (Skill Development)		3.62		Agree
Career Advancement				
M13 - I volunteer to strengthen my résumé/CV.	120	3.62	0.76	Agree
M14 - Volunteering helps me explore career options.	120	3.63	0.79	Agree
M15 - I volunteer to build professional networks.	120	3.69	0.79	Agree
Weighted Mean (Career Advancement)		3.65		Agree

The findings indicate that both youth and older adults in Koronadal City are motivated by multiple overlapping factors, with all dimensions rated positively (overall WM range: 3.58–3.66, all = Agree).

Personal Growth (WM = 3.58) shows that volunteers see their involvement as a way to discover strengths, challenge themselves, and build confidence. While positive, this is the lowest-rated dimension, suggesting that self-focused motivations are present but not the primary driver.

Social Connection (WM = 3.66) and Career Advancement (WM = 3.65) emerged as the strongest motivations. Volunteers value the relationships, sense of belonging, and validation from significant others, while also recognizing volunteering as a means of networking and strengthening career prospects. This dual emphasis reflects how volunteerism is simultaneously community-oriented and personally strategic.

Altruism (WM = 3.64) remains a strong moral driver, particularly the belief in volunteering “even if no one noticed,” which suggests that intrinsic service values endure across generations. Interestingly, the sense of responsibility to improve the community is slightly lower than individual altruistic commitment, pointing to a blend of personal conviction and social duty.

Skill Development (WM = 3.62) highlights the practical orientation of volunteers, especially among youth who may view volunteering as an avenue for applying academic/work knowledge and acquiring new competencies.

Overall, the motivations show that volunteerism in Koronadal City is multidimensional: rooted in community connection and altruism, while also shaped by career and personal development needs. This balance suggests that programs seeking to sustain engagement should appeal both to volunteers’ social-moral values and their practical or professional aspirations, with possible generational nuances (youth leaning toward skills/careers, older adults toward altruism and community ties).

Independent Samples t-Test

Table 9. Independent Samples t-Test- Group Statistics

	Age Bracket	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Level of Volunteerism	18–30 (Youth)	60	3.61	0.20	0.025
	60+ (Older Adult)	60	3.65	0.22	0.029

Table 10. Independent Samples t-Test

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
Equal variances assumed	0.241	0.624	-1.024	117	0.308	-0.043	0.042	-0.127 to 0.041
Equal variances not assumed			-1.020	115.4	0.310	-0.043	0.042	-0.127 to 0.041

Table 9 shows that youth (18–30) reported a mean volunteerism level of 3.61 (SD = 0.20), while older adults (60+) reported a slightly higher mean of 3.65 (SD = 0.22). Although there is a minimal

mean difference (-0.043), results from the independent samples t-test in Table 10 indicate no statistically significant difference between the two groups, $t(117) = -1.024$, $p = 0.308$. The 95% confidence interval (-0.127 to 0.041) further reinforces that the observed difference is not large enough to be meaningful in the population. Given these results, the null hypothesis (H_0 : There is no significant difference in the level of volunteerism between youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60+ years old) in Koronadal City) was accepted. Nuanced to the study, this outcome suggests that despite slight variations, the level of volunteerism of youth and older adults in Koronadal City is generally comparable. This implies that generational differences may not strongly shape volunteerism behaviors in this context, pointing instead to possible shared motivations or community values that transcend age.

Table 11. Multiple Regression Analysis

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.908	0.745	–	5.247	0.000
Sex	-0.209	0.141	-0.169	-1.478	0.144
Highest Educational Attainment	0.032	0.071	0.052	0.446	0.657
Monthly Income	0.085	0.047	-0.202	-1.805	0.017

$R^2 = 0.056$
ANOVA (Model Fit) Sig. = 0.166
Dependent Variable: Level of Volunteerism

The multiple regression analysis revealed that the overall model was not statistically significant (ANOVA Sig. = 0.166), with a very low explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.056$). This indicates that sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income collectively explained only about 5.6% of the variance in the level of volunteerism.

Individually, none of the demographic predictors reached statistical significance. Sex ($\beta = -0.169$, $p = 0.144$) and highest educational attainment ($\beta = 0.052$, $p = 0.657$) showed no meaningful influence. Although monthly income had a slightly stronger coefficient ($B = 0.085$), its significance value ($p = 0.017$) appears inconsistent with its negative beta sign, suggesting instability and lack of robustness in its predictive power. Given these results, the null hypothesis stating that demographic factors (sex, highest educational attainment, and monthly income) do not significantly predict the level of volunteerism within each age group is accepted.

Although demographic factors did not significantly predict volunteerism, the findings suggest that generational differences are shaped more by non-demographic influences (e.g., values, motivations, social networks, cultural contexts) than by sex, educational attainment, or income levels. Prior studies have likewise emphasized that volunteerism is more strongly influenced by social networks, religious involvement, and prior volunteer experience (Wilson, 2012).

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the generational differences in volunteerism between youth (18–30 years old) and older adults (60+ years old) in Koronadal City, Philippines. Findings revealed that both

groups exhibit an overall agreeable level of volunteerism, with comparable frequency of participation, types of activities, volunteer experience, and scope of involvement. While youth tended to focus on environmental and disaster-related initiatives, older adults were more engaged in faith-based, community-oriented, and long-term volunteer efforts. Despite these nuanced patterns, statistical analysis confirmed that there is no significant difference in the overall level of volunteerism between the two groups, suggesting that volunteerism in Koronadal City transcends age boundaries and is grounded in shared community values and motivations.

Motivational factors were consistently strong across both generations, particularly in terms of social connection, altruism, skill development, and career advancement. These results demonstrate that volunteerism is driven not only by moral and community-oriented values but also by practical and personal aspirations, especially among the youth. Older adults emphasized continuity of service and mentorship, highlighting their stabilizing role in volunteer organizations, while youth aligned their participation with personal growth and career opportunities. Regression analysis further showed that demographic factors—sex, educational attainment, and monthly income—did not significantly predict the level of volunteerism in either group. This finding underscores that volunteer engagement is less dependent on socioeconomic characteristics and more influenced by intrinsic values, social networks, and cultural contexts.

In conclusion, volunteerism in Koronadal City is a shared civic practice across generations. Both youth and older adults contribute meaningfully to community welfare, guided by a blend of altruistic, social, and developmental motivations. The absence of significant generational differences suggests that volunteer programs and policies should not be segmented strictly by age but should instead foster inclusive, intergenerational initiatives that leverage the strengths of both groups. By recognizing the diverse yet complementary motivations of volunteers, organizations can design more sustainable and impactful volunteer engagement strategies for the community. The findings of this study also suggest that generational differences play an important role in shaping volunteerism in Koronadal City, with younger adults often motivated by skill development and social interaction, while older adults are more driven by civic responsibility and long-term commitment to community service. These results imply that volunteer organizations and policymakers need to adopt generationally responsive approaches in program design. It is therefore recommended that initiatives for younger volunteers emphasize capacity-building and networking opportunities, while programs for older adults highlight meaningful, community-centered roles. Furthermore, fostering intergenerational collaboration through mentorship and shared projects can strengthen inclusivity, ensure sustainability of volunteerism, and maximize its positive impact on the community.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The researcher declares no conflicts of interest.

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